

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 81

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 81

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 81:0 For the choir director; 'on the Gittith. A <i>Psalm</i> of Asaph.</p>	<p>Psa. 81:1 לְמִנְצַח אֶל־הַגִּתִּית לְאַסָּף : 2 תְּהַדְּנֵנוּ לְאֱלֹהִים עֲוִינֵנוּ תְּהַדְּעֵנוּ לְאֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב : 3 שְׁאוּ־זַמְרָה וּתְנִי־תָהּ כַּנּוֹר נְעִים עִם־נָבֶל : 4 תִּקְעוּ בַתְּחֹדֶשׁ שׁוֹפָר בַּכֶּסֶה לַיּוֹם תִּגְנוּ : 5 כִּי חֶק לְיִשְׂרָאֵל הוּא כִּמְשֹׁפֵט לְאֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב : 6 עֲדוּת א בִּיהוֹסֵף שָׁמֹו בְּצֵאתוֹ עַל־אֶרֶץ מִצְרַיִם שְׁבַת לֹא־יִדְעָתִי אֲשַׁמֶּע : 7 הַסִּירוּתִי מִסֶּבֶל שְׂכָמוֹ כַּפְּיוֹ מִדָּוִד תִּעֲבֹרְנָה : 8 בַּצָּרָה קָרָאתָ וְאַתָּה לְצָדֵק אֲעֲנֶנּוּ בְּסֹתֵר רַעַם אֶבְחָנֶנּוּ עַל־מִי מְרִיבָה סִלָּה : 9 שְׁמַע עַמִּי וְאֶעֱיֶדְהָ בְּיָד יִשְׂרָאֵל אִם־תִּשְׁמַע־לִי : 10 לֹא־ יִהְיֶה בְּךָ אֵל זָר וְלֹא תִשְׁתַּחֲוֶה לְאֵל נֹכֵר : 11 אֲנֹכִי אִיהוָה אֱלֹהֶיךָ הַמַּעֲלֶדְךָ מֵאֶרֶץ מִצְרַיִם הַרְחֹב־פִּיךָ וְאִמְלֵאֲהוּ : 12 וְלֹא־שָׁמַע עַמִּי לְקוֹלִי וַיִּשְׂרָאֵל לֹא־אָבָה לִי : 13 וְאֲשַׁלַּחֲהוּ בְּשִׂרְיֹות לָבָם יִלְכוּ בְּמוֹעֲצוֹתֵיהֶם : 14 לוֹ עַמִּי שָׁמַע לִי יִשְׂרָאֵל בְּדַרְכֵי יִהְיֶה לָבוֹ : 15 כִּמְעַט אֲוִיבִיחֵם אֲכַנִּיעַ וְעַל צָרֵיהֶם אָשִׁיב יָדַי : 16 מִשְׁנֵאֵי יְהוָה יִכְתְּשׁוּ־לוֹ וַיְהִי עֲתָם לְעוֹלָם : 17 וַיִּאֲכִילֵהוּ</p>
<p>Psa. 81:1 ^aSing for joy to God our ^bstrength;</p>	
<p>Shout ^cjoyfully to the ^dGod of Jacob.</p>	
<p>² Raise a song, strike ^athe timbrel, The sweet sounding ^blyre with the ^charp.</p>	
<p>³ Blow the trumpet at the ^anew moon, At the full moon, on our ^bfeast day.</p>	
<p>⁴ For it is a statute for Israel, An ordinance of the God of Jacob.</p>	
<p>⁵ He established it for a testimony in Joseph When he ^{1a}went throughout the land of Egypt. I heard a ^blanguage that I did not know:</p>	
<p>Psa. 81:6 “I ^{1a}relieved his shoulder of the burden,</p>	
<p>His hands were freed from the ²basket.</p>	
<p>⁷ “You ^acalled in trouble and I rescued you; I ^banswered you in the hiding place of thunder;</p>	

I proved you at the ^cwaters of Meribah. ¹Selah.

⁸ “^aHear, O My people, and I will ¹admonish you;

O Israel, if you ^bwould listen to Me!

⁹ “Let there be no ^astrange god among you;

Nor shall you worship any foreign god.

¹⁰ “^aI, the LORD, am your God, Who brought you up from the land of Egypt;

^bOpen your mouth wide and I will ^cfill it.

Psa. 81:11 “But My people ^adid not listen to My voice,

And Israel did not ¹obey Me.

¹² “So I ^agave ¹them over to the stubbornness of their heart,

To walk in their own devices.

¹³ “Oh that My people ^awould listen to Me,

That Israel would ^bwalk in My ways!

¹⁴ “I would quickly ^asubdue their enemies

And ^bturn My hand against tr adversaries.

¹⁵ “^aThose who hate the LORD would ^bpretend obedience to Him,

And their time *of punishment* would be forever.

¹⁶ “¹But I would feed you with the ^{2a}finest of the wheat,

מִתְּלַב תִּטָּה וּמִצֹּר דְּבַשׁ
אֲשֶׁר יֵעָד :

<p>And with ^bhoney from the rock I would satisfy you.”</p>	
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References

Psalm 81:0

†Or *according to*

Psalm 81:1

^aPs 51:14; 59:16; 95:1

^bPs 46:1

^cPs 66:1; 95:2; 98:4

^dPs 84:8

Psalm 81:2

^aEx 15:20; Ps 149:3

^bPs 92:3; 98:5; 147:7

^cPs 108:2; 144:9

Psalm 81:3

^aNum 10:10

^bLev 23:24

Psalm 81:5

¹Lit *went out over*

^aEx 11:4

^bDeut 28:49; Ps 114:1; Jer 5:15

Psalm 81:6

¹Lit *removed his shoulder from*

²Or *brick load*

^aIs 9:4; 10:27

Psalm 81:7

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aEx 2:23; 14:10; Ps 50:15

^bEx 19:19; 20:18

^cEx 17:6, 7; Num 20:13; Ps 95:8

Psalm 81:8

¹Or *bear witness against*

^aPs 50:7

^bPs 95:7

Psalm 81:9

^aEx 20:3; Deut 5:7; 32:12; Ps 44:20; Is 43:12

Psalm 81:10

^aEx 20:2; Deut 5:6

^bJob 29:23

^cPs 37:4; 78:25; 107:9

Psalm 81:11

¹Lit *yield to*

^aDeut 32:15; Ps 106:25

Psalm 81:12

¹Lit *him*

^aJob 8:4; Acts 7:42; Rom 1:24, 26

Psalm 81:13

^aDeut 5:29; Ps 81:8; Is 48:18

^bPs 128:1; Is 42:24; Jer 7:23

Psalm 81:14

^aPs 18:47; 47:3

^bAmos 1:8

Psalm 81:15

^aRom 1:30

^bPs 18:44; 66:3

Psalm 81:16

¹Lit *He would feed him*

²Lit *fat*

^aDeut 32:14; Ps 147:14

^bDeut 32:13

Targum

Psa. 81:1 For praise; on the lyre that comes from Gath, composed by Asaph. ² Give praise in the presence of God, our strength; shout in the presence of the God of Jacob. ³ Lift up the voice in praise, and set out timbrels, the lyre whose sound is sweet with harps. ⁴ Blow the horn in the month of Tishri, in the month in which the day of our festivals is concealed. ⁵ For he made a covenant for Israel; it is a legal ruling of the God of Jacob. ⁶ He made it a testimony for Joseph, who did not go near the wife of his master; on that day he went out of the prison and ruled over all the land of Egypt. The tongue I did not know I have taught [and] heard. ⁷ I have removed his shoulder from servitude; his hands were taken away from casting clay into a pot. ⁸ In the time of the distress of Egypt, you called and I delivered you; I made you fast in the secret place where my presence is, where wheels of fire call out before him; I tested you by the waters of Dispute forever. ⁹ Hear, O my people, and I will bear witness for you, O Israel, if you will accept my word. ¹⁰ There shall not be among you worshippers of a foreign idol, and you shall not bow down to a profane idol. ¹¹ I am the LORD your God, who brought you up from the land of Egypt; open wide your mouth with the words of Torah, and I will fill it with all good things. ¹² But my people did not receive my voice; and Israel did not want my word. ¹³ And I expelled them for the thoughts of their heart, they went away in their wicked counsel. ¹⁴ Would that my people had listened to me – that Israel would walk in my ways! ¹⁵ In a little while I will humble their enemies, and I will turn my strong blow against their enemies. ¹⁶ The enemies of the LORD will be false to him; and their harshness will last forever. ¹⁷ But he will feed him with the best of wheat bread; and I will satisfy you with honey from the rock.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

In this Psalm, Israel beseeched the LORD to free His people from their Babylonian Exile. This Psalm celebrates the divine salvation which ended Israel's servitude in Egypt. The process of Egyptian salvation started six months earlier on the first day of Tishrei, Rosh HaShannah, when the Israelites stopped working as slaves for the Egyptian taskmasters (from Rosh Hashanah 11a of the Talmud). This Psalm was designated to accompany the Temple sacrifices on Rosh Hashanah (from Rosh Hashanah 30b of the Talmud).

Superscript

The meaning of the Hebrew word **הַגְּבִירָה** is unknown. This Psalm visualizes the splendor of which grapes. Rabbi Hirsch believes this word means wine-pressing or some part of the process.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, upon the “wine pressing” by Asaf.

Verse one

The phrase “God of Jacob” raises the speculation that the Psalmist knew Israel followed the LORD's Laws of the Torah. However, like Jacob, they got into the gray areas and perhaps crossed the line in a few ways. Jacob was a trickster in that he fooled his brother Esau into giving him the birthright and the blessing of their father, Isaac. The Psalmist is reminding Israel that they have been tricksters before the LORD.

Stir up jubilation to God, our strength; waken homage to the God of Jacob.

Verse three

This verse refers to the holy day of Rosh Hashanah.

But blow the shofar at the New Moon on the day of the veiling of the moon for the day of our festival.

Verse five

The people were to emulate Joseph, who remained faithful to the LORD's spiritual and moral truth and purity even in the face of a godless nation. The exiled people needed to stay loyal to the LORD while exiled in Babylon.

He had appointed it in Joseph as a testimony when He went forth over the land of Egypt; I shall henceforth hear the speech of one Whom I had not known before.

Verse seven

The waters of Meribah are the waters of contention.

You called in distress, and I have made you free; so I shall answer you even hidden in thunder; I shall test you at the Waters of Contention. Meditate on this verse.

Verse nine

An "alien god" or "foreign god" was a god who was served by the Gentile nations. The Psalmist warns the people of Israel, even in exile, they must not allow the culture that surrounded them to penetrate them. The gods of Babylon must never replace the LORD.

There shall be no alien god within you, nor shall you prostrate yourself before a foreign god.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

